

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INFECTIONS AND B-THALASSEMIA

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ABSTRACT

In the article authors represent an analytical review of current evidence on infectious complications in β -thalassemia, integrating data from pathophysiological research, clinical studies, and recent international guidelines. Infections remain a major cause of morbidity and mortality despite advances in therapy in beta-thalassemia patients. Chronic anemia, iron overload, and splenic dysfunction lead to significant disturbances in innate and adaptive immunity. Functional hyposplenism or splenectomy increases susceptibility to encapsulated bacteria, while excess iron promotes oxidative stress and macrophage dysfunction, facilitating siderophilic infections. Chronic transfusions expose patients to transfusion-transmitted viruses, and chelation therapy—particularly with deferoxamine—may further modify infection risk. The review emphasizes evidence-based prevention through vaccination, antibiotic prophylaxis, careful chelation, monitoring, and patient education. By summarizing current data and guideline recommendations, we highlight the importance of integrated infection control as a key component of modern β -thalassemia management.

Keywords: β -thalassemia, infections, splenectomy, iron overload, chelation therapy, immune dysfunction, prevention.

Introduction

Beta-thalassemia is an inherited disorder of hemoglobin synthesis in which mutations in the β -globin gene lead to reduced (β^+) or absent (β^0) production of β -globin chains. The consequence is chronic anemia, hemolysis, and compensatory erythroid hyperplasia. The severe forms with pronounced transfusion dependence constitute transfusion-dependent beta-thalassemia (TDT), comprising both homozygous patients and those with compound heterozygosity. This group additionally requires lifelong iron chelation therapy. As a result, life expectancy has increased substantially, but new management challenges have emerged. Notably, infectious complications remain a major cause of morbidity and mortality and rank among the top three causes of death in TDT. Leading risk factors include chronic hemolysis and reticuloendothelial dysfunction, secondary iron overload, splenectomy, and exposure to infectious agents due to hypertransfusion programs.

Objective, Subject, Material and Methods

Objective: To present the principal mechanisms, risk factors, and preventive strategies related to infectious complications in patients with β -thalassemia (immune dysregulation; the impact of transfusion and iron chelation therapy; splenectomy).

Subject: Infectious events in patients with β -thalassemia, their relationship to disease characteristics and chelation therapy and preventive strategies.

Material and methods: We reviewed key publications and guidelines indexed in PubMed, Scopus, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar for 1990–2025 focusing on the frequency and spectrum of infections, pathogenetic mechanisms of infectious risk, and the roles of chelation and transfusion therapy. Based on

these data, we extracted some practical messages for treatment teams and patients with beta-thalassemia.

Epidemiological data

Infectious complications in β -thalassemia have been recognized as a substantial clinical problem since the late 1980s. In an early large retrospective series, Issaragrisil et al. (1987) reported infections as a leading cause of hospitalization and death [1]. Wang et al. (2003) observed a rate of severe bacterial infections of 0.23 per 100 patient-years; 78% of episodes occurred in splenectomized patients, and mortality in severe septicemia reached 10.5% [2]. In Northern Taiwan, Chern et al. (2007) reported that infections accounted for 16.7% of all adverse events, with declining sepsis-related mortality [3]. In the Mediterranean region, Borgna-Pignatti et al. (2004) noted that infections and cardiac complications together accounted for approximately 25% of deaths and documented high hepatitis B and C (HBV/HCV) carriage, a basis for later cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) [4]. More recent data from Taher indicate that infections account for 20–40% of all hospitalizations, and despite virological screening, vaccination programs, and modern chelation, they remain the second most frequent cause of death after cardiac disease [5]. In a long retrospective cohort, Forni and colleagues ranked infections as the third leading cause of death over 59 years of follow-up [6].

General principles of immune dysregulation in thalassemia

Role of functional asplenia and splenectomy

The spleen is a key secondary lymphoid organ with both filtration and immunological functions [7–9]. First, its filtration function provides mechanical blood clearance and early removal of microorganisms from

the circulation. In the red pulp, macrophages and reticuloendothelial cells phagocytose senescent erythrocytes, platelets, and pathogens [1]. Second, splenic macrophages phagocytose and process antigens and present them to T-lymphocytes, thereby initiating adaptive immune responses [10,11]. Third, the white pulp is rich of B- and T-lymphocytes, which execute specialized immune functions [12]. Fourth, the marginal zone harbors memory B-cells that underpin rapid secondary humoral responses to capsulated bacteria such as *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Neisseria meningitidis*, and *Haemophilus influenzae* type b. Loss or functional deficiency of the spleen increases the risk of severe complications, including fatal overwhelming post-splenectomy infection (OPSI) [13]. The risk is highest in the first 2–3 years after surgery—particularly for *S. pneumoniae*, *H. influenzae*, and *N. meningitidis*—but persists lifelong [9,14].

Toxicity of iron in iron overload state

Pathological iron accumulation increases the pool of non-transferrin-bound iron (NTBI), a toxic fraction that injures diverse tissues and immune cells and fosters severe, recurrent infections. Core mechanisms of iron toxicity include:

a). Oxidative stress and impaired phagocytosis. Iron participates in Fenton reaction, generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) that damage lipid membranes, mitochondria, and enzymes in neutrophils and macrophages. This leads to macrophage dysfunction and reduced bactericidal activity. Deicher et al. found that in secondary haemosiderosis, serum ferritin level correlates with impaired phagocytosis and elevated TNF- α [15]. Iron-loaded macrophages also produce less IL-12 and TNF- α [16].

b). Disordered hepcidin regulation. In thalassemia, hepcidin levels are low, further amplifying intestinal iron absorption and NTBI [17].

c). T-cell imbalance. Iron overload shifts the CD8⁺/CD4⁺ balance and suppresses T-helper proliferation, impairing cell-mediated immunity with reduced

IL-2 and IFN- γ . In severe siderosis, mitogen-induced T-cell proliferation and Th1 responses are blunted [18,19].

d). Humoral defects. Iron-loaded macrophages produce less IL-12 and TNF- α , weakening B-cell co-stimulation; serum IgG2 and IgM (critical for defense against capsulated bacteria) can fall [16].

Kruetzmann et al. (2003) demonstrated that IgM memory B-cells protective against *S. pneumoniae* arise in the spleen; these cells are markedly reduced after splenectomy or in congenital asplenia, with poor anti-pneumococcal responses [11]. Each unit of transfused packed red cells delivers ~200–250 mg of iron; with chronic therapy this accumulates to >0.5–1 g per month. Donor-derived cytokines and microparticles may further perturb immune homeostasis and favor siderophilic infections [20].

Role of iron chelation therapy

Iron chelators have bidirectional effects on infection risk. Deferoxamine (DFO) can serve as a siderophore-like iron source for *Yersinia* spp. and *Mucorales*, facilitating growth. Fatal infections have been reported with long-term DFO [21]. Deferiprone (DFP) does not directly promote bacterial growth but, may cause severe neutropenia and modulate cytokine balance [22].

Role of chronic transfusion therapy

Repeated transfusions increase the risk of transfusion-transmitted infections such as HBV, HCV, HIV, and parvovirus B19 [23]. Transfused lymphocytes may transiently persist, contributing to a state of chronic immune activation and susceptibility to opportunistic infections [24]. Stored red cells accumulate free heme, iron, and microparticles that increase oxidative stress and activate inflammatory pathways, suppressing macrophage and T-cell function [19,25]. Fig.1 schematically illustrates multifactorial profile of infection susceptibility in β thalassemia.

Fig.1 Multifactorial causes of immune dysfunction and infection susceptibility in β thalassemia

Clinical data

Infectious spectrum. The range of pathogens is broad—bacterial, viral, and fungal. Table 1 summarizes common pathogens and predisposing factors. In splenectomized patients, capsulated bacteria predominate (*S. pneumoniae*, *N. meningitidis*, *H. influenzae*).

Iron overload favors Gram-negative pathogens, including *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Vibrio vulnificus*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Transfusion therapy remains linked to chronic viral infections (HBV, HCV, HIV). With additional immunosuppression (e.g., post-transplant), latent viruses such as CMV and parvovirus B19 may reactivate, and invasive fungal disease may occur.

Table 1.

Most frequent pathogens in patients with beta-thalassemia

Pathogen group	Typical agents	Main predisposing factor	Typical clinical manifestations / infections
Obligate pathogens			
Bacteria	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	Splenectomy, asplenia	Sepsis, pneumonia, meningitis
	<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i> type b	Splenectomy, children <10 yrs	Meningitis, bacteremia
	<i>Neisseria meningitidis</i>	Splenectomy, immune deficiency	Meningitis, sepsis
	<i>Salmonella typhi</i> , <i>S. paratyphi</i>	Chronic anemia, iron load	Typhoid, enteritis
Viruses	HBV, HCV, HIV	Transfusion transmission	Chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis, immunodeficiency
	Parvovirus B19	Hemolysis, suppressed erythropoiesis	Aplastic crisis
	CMV, EBV	Immunosuppression, transfusions	Reactivation, mononucleosis
Fungi & parasites	<i>Candida albicans</i>	Antibiotics, immune deficiency	Oropharyngeal/systemic candidiasis

Pathogen group	Typical agents	Main predisposing factor	Typical clinical manifestations / infections
	<i>Plasmodium</i> spp.	Endemic regions	Severe malaria, anemia
Conditionally pathogenic (opportunistic)			
Gram-negative bacteria	<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>	Deferoxamine (siderophore effect)	Sepsis, enterocolitis, mesenteric adenitis
	<i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	Iron overload, DFO therapy	Sepsis, cellulitis, necrotizing fasciitis
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Iron load, liver injury	Pneumonia, abscesses, bacteremia
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Neutropenia, catheters	Pneumonia, sepsis, otitis
Gram-positive bacteria	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>S. epidermidis</i>	Neutropenia, catheters	Catheter-related/skin infections
	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	Long-term chelation	UTIs, endocarditis
Fungi	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Severe neutropenia (DFP)	Pulmonary aspergillosis
	Mucorales spp.	Iron load, diabetes	Rhino-cerebral/pulmonary mucormycosis
Latent/reactivating viruses	CMV, EBV	Iron load, immunosuppression	Hepatitis, mononucleosis, pancytopenia
	HSV-1/2, VZV	Chronic anemia, stress	Herpes zoster and other herpesvirus infections

Marks under the Table 1. **HBV** – Hepatitis B virus; **HCV** – Hepatitis C virus, **HIV** – Human immunodeficiency virus, **Parvovirus B19** – Human parvovirus B19; **CMV** – Cytomegalovirus, **EBV** – Epstein–Barr virus **VZV**–Varicella Zoster Virus

Infections of special interest in beta-thalassemia

Bacterial infections are a major life-threatening complication in TDT [26]. Risk reflects combined effects of anatomical/functional asplenia, iron overload, chronic inflammation, and immune dysregulation. As noted, capsulated bacteria dominate with splenic dysfunction, whereas iron overload favors Gram-negative organisms. Patients with thalassemia are particularly vulnerable to OPSI after splenectomy. Mortality remains 50–70%. *S. pneumoniae* is the leading cause, though other capsulated bacteria are also implicated. The course is fulminant, often progressing within hours from nonspecific prodrome (fatigue, chills, myalgias, low-grade fever) to high fever, tachycardia, hypotension, and septic shock, with frequent DIC, renal and respiratory failure, purpura fulminans, and meningitis. Without immediate antibiotics, death may occur within 24–48 h [27,28]. Among Gram-negative pathogens of particular relevance is *Yersinia enterocolitica*. While often commensal in immunocompetent hosts, iron overload and DFO therapy create a permissive niche for virulence and severe disease. Abdominal pain, diarrhea, and vomiting predominate; rarely, fulminant sepsis with visceral abscesses occurs. *Yersinia enterocolitica* should be considered in abdominal pain, especially in poorly chelated patients or those on DFO. As serology is unreliable, microbiology from abscess material may be required [29]. Other Gram-negative pathogens include *Klebsiella* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., and *E. coli*. Infections caused by obligate pathogens show similar clinical features to those in the general population. In

unvaccinated patients, *H. influenzae* remains a challenge, although consistent vaccination provides robust protection.

Fungal infections are led by *Mucorales*. Here the association with iron overload and DFO is well established. Other invasive mycoses as aspergillosis and cryptococcosis are predominantly a concern with additional risk factors (e.g., post-transplant immunosuppression).

Chelators and their rspecific contribution to the development of bacterial infections

Three chelators are widely used—DFO, DFP, and DFX—with distinct chemistry, pharmacokinetics, and immunologic effects. DFO remains the historical standard for severe siderosis but serves as a xenosiderophore for certain microbes, increasing risk of *Yersinia* sepsis and *mucormycosis*—particularly in patients with high iron burden [30,31]. DFP is an oral and mitochondria-permeant drug. Its key adverse event is idiosyncratic causing neutropenia/agranulocytosis ($\approx 1\text{--}2\%$) rather than a dose-dependent effect [24,32]. Sherif M. et al., 2024 reported $<1\%$ infection incidence over $>113,000$ patient-years; serious infections occurred only with profound neutropenia ($\text{ANC} < 0.1 \times 10^9/\text{L}$), most often within the first 6–12 months of therapy [33]. DFX appears to carry a lower infectious risk than DFO/DFP, likely by reducing labile iron and normalizing cytokine responses.

Real -world data on infections in beta- thalassaemia

Clinical studies on bacterial infections

In a 15-year prospective cohort (1971–2002), Wang et al. (2003) detailed both incidence and clinical course of severe bacterial infections [1]. The most frequent pathogens were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (39%), *Escherichia coli* (22%), and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (11%). Presentations included bacteremia, sepsis, pneumonia, and peritonitis; septicemia mortality reached 10.5%. Higher ferritin (>2500 ng/mL) predicted increased Gram-negative sepsis, and splenectomy independently predicted severe infection—supporting continuous prophylaxis (vaccination, penicillin) and stringent iron control. In a subsequent regional series of 136 patients with severe β -thalassemia, Chern et al. (2007) identified splenectomy and elevated ferritin as risk factors. Clinical syndromes included bacteremia, pneumonia, and hepatic abscess; *K. pneumoniae* predominated, followed by *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. Mortality was \approx 11%, underscoring the need for ongoing antibiotic prevention.

Alzhrani (2020) retrospectively analyzed 231 patients (214 TDT, 17 NTDT) from 2014–2018 (mean age 22 years). Severe bacterial infection occurred in 16.5%; 65.8% had positive cultures. Gram-negative bacteria predominated (*E. coli* 24.1%, *K. pneumoniae* 13.8%), *S. aureus* led among Gram-positive bacteria (13.8%). No significant associations were found with splenectomy, prophylactic antibiotics, or chelator type ($P > 0.05$), consistent with the mitigating impact of preventive practices and reflecting a lower infection rate (16.5%) versus historical 22–66% [34]. A recent single-center cohort of 303 transfusion-dependent patients followed for 15 years (2007–2022) reported 72/303 (23.8%) with positive blood-culture-confirmed infections; *E. coli* was most frequent, followed by *K. pneumoniae* and *S. aureus*, paralleling Alzhrani [20]. Heavier iron burden, estimated by serum ferritin was a key risk factor. Notably, combined chelation (e.g., DFO + DFP) was associated with lower infection frequency (OR = 0.02; $p = 0.01$), suggesting protection via more effective iron control and possibly reduced DFO-related siderophore effects at lower doses. Overall, bacterial infections have remained a leading complication

for >3 decades despite improved transfusion and chelation, with highest risk in splenectomized patients and those with substantial iron overload.

Transfusion-related infections

Despite improved donor screening, HCV prevalence in thalassemia remains 10–30% depending on region [35]. HCV augments oxidative stress and immune dysregulation and drives chronic liver injury (cirrhosis and elevated HCC risk). Before universal HBsAg screening, HBV rates reached 40–60%. ELISA and NAT have markedly reduced risk, though “window periods” and low-level viremia persist. Lai et al. reported a residual HBV risk of about 1 per 350,000 transfusions in highly regulated settings. HBV likewise causes chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis, and higher HCC risk, particularly with concomitant iron overload [36].

Post-screening transfusion-mediated HIV transmission is exceedingly rare, though legacy coinfections exist in patients transfused before the 1990s, further compromising immunity [37]. Parvovirus B19 can also be transfusion-transmitted and may cause aplastic crisis in chronic hemolysis. In thalassemia it acutely worsens anemia. Rossi et al. reported up to 15% B19 seropositivity among multiply transfused patients [38].

How to prevent and control infectious complications

Prevention is central to comprehensive care, particularly in the context of splenectomy, iron overload, transfusion exposure, and immunosuppression. Current Thalassaemia International Federation (TIF, 2021) and CDC (2023) guidance emphasizes vaccination, antibiotic prophylaxis, virological surveillance, and patient/family education [39,40].

Vaccine prophylaxis

Patients—especially those with splenectomy or functional asplenia—should receive expanded immunization against pneumococcus, meningococcus, and *H. influenzae* type b. All patients should be immunized against HBV. Annual influenza vaccination and a full COVID-19 schedule with boosters are recommended. According to TIF, vaccination reduces severe septic episodes by up to 70% in splenectomized patients.

Table 2

Summarizes recommended schedules and indications (adapted from TIF [39]).

Vaccine	Schedule and revaccination	Comment
Pneumococcal (PCV13 → PPSV23)	PCV13 once; PPSV23 \geq 8 weeks later; revaccinate at 5 years	Protects against <i>S. pneumoniae</i>
Meningococcal (MenACWY, MenB)	MenACWY: 2 doses \geq 8 weeks apart; 5-year boosters; MenB: 2–3 doses	Indicated for splenectomy/asplenia
<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i> type b (Hib)	Single adult catch-up if missed in childhood	Prevents Hib disease
Hepatitis B (HBV)	3 doses (0–1–6 months), check anti-HBs	Mandatory in transfused patients
Influenza	Annually	Particularly with hepatic/cardiac disease
COVID-19	Full schedule + boosters	Recommended for all with chronic illness

Principles of antimicrobial prophylaxis

Post-splenectomy, penicillin V is commonly recommended and erythromycin may be used for penicillin allergy. Regular antibiotic prophylaxis substantially reduces OPSI risk from capsulated organisms [28]. In suspected *Yersinia* infection or mucormycosis while on DFO, patient must discontinue DFO immediately and initiate appropriate antimicrobial therapy. Regular HBV/HCV surveillance is advisable and chronic HCV should be treated with DAAs to achieve viral eradication and reduce progression to fibrosis, cirrhosis, and HCC.

General recommendations and conclusion

Patients with β -thalassemia, particularly those who have undergone splenectomy, should be educated to recognize infection as a medical emergency. **Seeking urgent medical attention at the very first sign of fever** (≥ 38.0 °C/100.4 °F), chills, rapidly increasing fatigue, dyspnea, severe headache, confusion, or new petechial rash is crucial, since **waiting for symptoms to “declare themselves” may be life-threatening** in individuals at risk of overwhelming post-splenectomy infection (OPSI). Preventive behavior plays an equally important role. **Avoiding contact with people who have active respiratory or gastrointestinal infections** is strongly recommended, as is **minimizing exposure to crowded indoor spaces during epidemic outbreaks**. When avoidance is not possible, the patient should adopt protective measures such as **wearing a mask and practicing meticulous hand hygiene**. During iron-chelation therapy, close hematologic monitoring remains essential. Patients receiving deferasiprone should have **regular leukocyte count assessments**, and any sore throat, fever, or mouth ulcer should prompt **immediate medical consultation** because of the potential for drug-induced neutropenia. Every patient who is asplenic should **carry a medical alert card or bracelet** clearly indicating “*Asplenic patient – infection risk*,” together with a list of current medications and vaccination records[40]. This simple measure facilitates rapid and appropriate intervention in emergencies. Finally, infection prevention should be viewed as an ongoing process. **Keeping all immunizations up to date with adherence to prescribed chelation therapy and regular clinical follow-up**, are key elements in reducing infectious morbidity.

In conclusion, effective infection prevention in β -thalassemia requires an integrated strategy combining vaccination, antibiotic prophylaxis, virological monitoring, and patient education. Implementation of these measures may reduce infectious morbidity and improve long-term outcomes in this vulnerable population.

References

1. Issaragrisil S, Wanachiwanawin W, Bhuripanyo K, Benjasuratwong Y, Piankijagum A, Wasi P. Infection in thalassemia: a retrospective study of 1,018 patients with beta-thalassemia/Hb E disease. *Birth Defects Orig Artic Ser.* 1987;23(5A):505–511. PMID: 3689939.
2. Wang SC, Lin KH, Chern JP, et al. Severe bacterial infection in transfusion-dependent patients with thalassemia major. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2003;37(7):984–988. doi:10.1086/377536.
3. Chern JP, Su S, Lin KH, et al. Survival, mortality, and complications in patients with β -thalassemia major in Northern Taiwan. *Pediatr Blood Cancer.* 2007;48(6):550–554. doi:10.1002/pbc.20828.
4. Borgna-Pignatti C, Cappellini MD, De Stefano P, Del Vecchio GC, Forni GL, Gamberini MR, et al. Survival and complications in thalassemia. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 2005;1054:40–47. doi:10.1196/annals.1345.006. PMID: 16339650.
5. Taher AT, Musallam KM, Cappellini MD. Thalassaemia. *Lancet.* 2020;395(10230):155–167. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(19)31803-3.
6. Forni GL, Ganesin B, Musallam KM, Longo F, Rosso R, Lisi R, et al.; Webthal® Project. Overall and complication-free survival in a large cohort of patients with β -thalassemia major followed over 50 years. *Am J Hematol.* 2023;98(3):381–387. doi:10.1002/ajh.26798. PMID: 36588408.
7. Mebius RE, Kraal G. Structure and function of the spleen. *Nat Rev Immunol.* 2005;5(8):606–616. doi:10.1038/nri1669.
8. Di Sabatino A, Carsetti R, Corazza GR. Post-splenectomy and hyposplenic states. *Lancet.* 2011;378(9785):86–97. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(10)61493-6.
9. Lenti MV, Luu S, Carsetti R, et al. Asplenia and spleen hypofunction. *Nat Rev Dis Primers.* 2022;8(1):71. doi:10.1038/s41572-022-00388-0.
10. Bronte V, Pittet MJ. The spleen in local and systemic regulation of immunity. *Immunity.* 2013;39(5):806–818. doi: 10.1016/j.immuni.2013.10.010.
11. Kruetzmann S, Rosado MM, Weber H, Germing U, Tournilhac O, Peter HH, et al. Human immunoglobulin M memory B cells controlling *Streptococcus pneumoniae* infections are generated in the spleen. *J Exp Med.* 2003;197(7):939–945. doi:10.1084/jem.20022020.
12. Steiniger BS. Human spleen microanatomy: why mice do not suffice. *Immunology.* 2015;145(3):334–346. doi:10.1111/imm.12469.
13. Bisharat N, Omari H, Lavi I, Raz R. Risk of infection and death among post-splenectomy patients. *J Infect.* 2001;43(3):182–186. doi:10.1053/jinf.2001.0906.
14. Cappellini MD, Cohen A, Eleftheriou A, et al. *Guidelines for the Clinical Management of Thalassaemia.* 2nd Revised Edition. Nicosia (CY): Thalassaemia International Federation; 2008. Chapter 10: Splenectomy in β -thalassaemia. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK173963>
15. Deicher R, Hörl WH. Hepcidin: a molecular link between inflammation and anaemia. *Clin Exp Immunol.* 2003;132(3):509–516. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2249.2003.02163.x.
16. Dixit A, Chatterjee T, Mishra P, et al. Correlation of serum ferritin levels with immunoglobulin subclasses and infection rate in multitransfused thalassemia major patients. *J Clin Immunol.* 2012;32(4):798–806. doi:10.1007/s10875-012-9670-4.

17. Ganz T, Nemeth E. Heparin and iron homeostasis. *Blood*. 2012;119(17):4391–4397. doi:10.1182/blood-2011-11-370932.
18. Wong P, Fuller M, Gleagle JM. Thalassemia and the immune system: a review. *Br J Haematol*. 2015;168(6):874–883. doi:10.1111/bjh.13208.
19. Asadov CHD. Immunologic abnormalities in β -thalassemia. *J Blood Disord Transfus*. 2015;6(6):224. doi:10.4172/2155-9864.1000224.
20. Mansory E.M., Abdulrahman L.M., Osman B., Alsiyufi S.M., Ruckn A.F., Aljedaani M., Hassan N., Barefah A.S., Alahwal H.M., Daghistani Y., Bahashwan S.M., Almohammadi A.T., Radhwi O.O. Predisposing factors to infections in thalassemia syndrome patients. *Mediterr J Hematol Infect Dis* 2025, 17(1): e2025055
21. Boelaert JR. The role of desferrioxamine in infections: a double-edged sword. *N Engl J Med*. 1993; 329(19):1305–1309. doi:10.1056/NEJM199310283291805.
22. Poggiali E, Cassinerio E, Zanaboni L, Cappellini MD. An update on iron chelation therapy. *Blood Transfus*. 2017;15(5):422–434. doi:10.2450/2017.0136-17.
23. Amirhashchi F, Azaran A, Seyedian SS, Jalilian S, Keikhaei B. Occult hepatitis B virus infection among β -thalassemia major patients in Ahvaz City, Iran. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2021;106(1):174–181. doi:10.4269/ajtmh.21-0785. PMID: 34607305; PMCID: PMC8733492.
24. Ehsanipour F, Faranoush P, Foroughi-Gilvae MR, Sadighnia N, Fallahpour M, Motamedi M, et al. Evaluation of immune system in patients with transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia: a descriptive cross-sectional study. *Health Sci Rep*. 2023;6(3):e1069. doi:10.1002/hsr2.1069. PMID: 36917768; PMCID: PMC9997061.
25. Hod EA, Zhang N, Sokol SA, et al. Transfusion of red blood cell units increases plasma interleukin-6 and TNF- α levels. *Blood*. 2010;115(19):4284–4292. doi:10.1182/blood-2009-10-246983.
26. Lee GM, Wessels MR, Richardson TE. Preventing infections in children and adults with asplenia. *Hematology Am Soc Hematol Educ Program*. 2020;2020(1):328–336. doi:10.1182/hematology.2020000181. Available from: <https://ashpublications.org/hematology/article/2020/1/328/474295>
27. Okabayashi T, Hanazaki K. Overwhelming postsplenectomy infection syndrome in adults: a clinically preventable disease. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2008;14(2):176–179. doi:10.3748/wjg.14.176. PMID: 18186551; PMCID: PMC2675110.
28. Serio B, Pezzullo L, Giudice V, Fontana R, Annunziata S, Ferrara I, et al. OPSI threat in hematological patients. *Transl Med UniSa*. 2013;6:2–10. PMID: 24251241; PMCID: PMC3829791.
29. Vento S, Cainelli F, Cesario F. Infections and thalassemia. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2006;6(4):226–233. doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(06)70437-8.
30. Autenrieth IB, Reissbrodt R, Saken E, Berner R, Vogel U, Rabsch W, Heesemann J. Desferrioxamine-promoted virulence of *Yersinia enterocolitica* in mice depends on both desferrioxamine type and mouse strain. *J Infect Dis*. 1994;169(3):562–567. doi:10.1093/infdis/169.3.562. PMID: 8158027.
31. Boelaert JR, de Locht M, Van Cutsem J, Kerrels V, Cantinieaux B, Verdonck A, et al. Mucormycosis during desferrioxamine therapy is a siderophore-mediated infection. *J Clin Invest*. 1993;91(5):1979–1986. doi:10.1172/JCI116419. PMID: 8486769; PMCID: PMC288195.
32. Tricta F, Utrecht J, Galanello R, Connelly J, Rozova A, Spino M, et al. Deferiprone-induced agranulocytosis: 20 years of clinical observations. *Am J Hematol*. 2016;91(10):1026–1031. doi:10.1002/ajh.24479. PMID: 27415835; PMCID: PMC5129477.
33. Badawy SM, Palmblad J, Tricta F, Temin NT, Fradette C, Lin L, et al. Rates of severe neutropenia and infection risk in patients treated with deferiprone: 28 years of data. *Blood Adv*. 2024;8(21):5641–5649. doi:10.1182/bloodadvances.2023012316.
34. Alzhrani FS, Algethmi FA, Makin MA, Alqarni RM, Alzahrani A, Alghamdi M, et al. Prevalence and risk factors of severe bacterial infections in thalassemia patients. *Curr Pediatr Res*. 2020;24(4):231–238. Available from: <https://www.currentpediatrics.com/articles/prevalence-and-risk-factors-of-severe-bacterial-infections-in-thalassemia-patients-14519.html>.
35. Taher AT, Musallam KM, Cappellini MD. Thalassaemia. *Lancet*. 2020; 395(10230):155–167. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(19)31803-3.
36. Lai ME, Dore F, et al. Infection risk and immune dysfunction in thalassemia. *Haematologica*. 2010;95(9):1589–1595.
37. Modell B, Darlison M. Global epidemiology of haemoglobin disorders and derived service indicators. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2008;86(6):480–487. doi:10.2471/BLT.06.036673.
38. Rossi G, et al. Infectious complications in thalassemia: transfusion-related and immune aspects. *Transfusion*. 2010; 50 (10): 2260–2266. doi:10.1111/j.1537-2995.2010.02667.x.
39. Cappellini MD, et al. *Guidelines for the Management of Transfusion-Dependent Thalassaemia (TDT)*. 4th ed. Nicosia (CY): Thalassaemia International Federation; 2021.
40. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). *Guidelines for Vaccinating Asplenic and Hypo-splenic Patients*. Atlanta, GA: CDC; 2023. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/vaccines>.